

D6.2 Extract of the project data from the LIFE KPI webtool

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Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an initial snapshot of the PRISTINE Project KPIs, gathered during the first months of the project. Deviations and changes from the KPIs described at a proposal stage (Part C) are mentioned. An export excel file of the KPIs filled in the webtool is provided as an Annex.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CEC	Contaminants of emerging concern
DW	Drinking water
DWTP	Drinking water treatment plant
EC	European Commission
WW	Wastewater
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

Introduction

Key Performance Indicators are a set of values used to measure the success of a certain endeavour in different fields: Technical, Financial, Administrative. They are set up-front as a target and then compared with final outcomes to assess performance. Specifically for the LIFE programme KPIs are a set of Environmental and Socio-economic indicators used to measure the impact of the LIFE programme funding.

According to the LIFE Regulations (1293/2013 and 2021/783) the LIFE programme shall be assessed against indicators (named Key Project Level Indicators - KPIs). For this purpose, the LIFE programme gathers information on KPIs from applicants and successful LIFE beneficiaries, at different stages of the proposal preparation and execution.

At proposal stage, the expected results of a project in terms of environmental and also socio-economic benefits is estimated using a set of KPIs. Once a project is funded, the coordinating beneficiary must record the project results through the KPI webtool. This should be done minimum twice during the project's lifetime. The first time should be during the initial stages of the project (within the first nine months of the project's implementation) and the second time) should be at final report stage.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an initial snapshot of the PRISTINE Project KPIs, gathered during the first months of the project. Deviations and changes from the KPIs described at a proposal stage (Part C) are mentioned. An export excel file of the KPIs filled in the webtool is provided as an Annex.

1 Indicator context

The LIFE PRISTINE project addresses the ‘Water & Resource Efficiency’ Priority area, and the Thematic priority ‘Water’. The selection of the priority and sub-priority area determines a set of mandatory KPIs to report on, as it is described in next Section.

In line, the Overreaching context the ‘Water bodies’ is selected and three specific contexts created:

- Murcia - WW: the context where wastewater demonstration activities will take place.
- Pais Vasco - DW: the context Where drinking water demonstration activities will take place.
- General context, being the sum of the two previous specific context, to be used to report cross-cutting KPIs linked to communication, networking and socioeconomic impact KPIs.

2 Project settings and indicator selection

The LIFE Programme requires to report on a series of mandatory KPIs and Sections, some of them linked to project topics and others mandatory for all LIFE Projects. These mandatory KPIs will appear as pre-selected (pre-ticked) in the KPIs webtool. For the present project, the following KPIs are selected:

- 1. Project area, length, and population
 - 1.5. B. Project work area
 - 1.6. B. Humans impacted by the project
- 2.B Water (including the marine environment)
 - 2.2.B Reduction in area of length of surface fresh water bodies or volume of ground water bodies whose status is affected by issues addressed by the project.
 - 2.4.B. Pressure(s) or Risk(s) addressed.
 - 2.4.2.B Water efficiency - Reduction in new water produced/supplied, due to appropriate water saving measures.
 - 2.4.3.B Water Pollution - Diffuse or Point source pollution
- 4.B Resource efficiency and Waste (including energy, circular economy, and forests) Water (not pre-selected but selected by project partners)
 - 4.1.B Energy
 - 4.1.1.B Primary energy consumption reduction.
- 8.B Climate Change Mitigation (not pre-selected but selected by project partners)
 - 4.1.B Reduction of Greenhouse gas emissions
- 11. B. Information and awareness
 - 11.1. B. Website
 - 11.2 B. Other tools for reaching/raising awareness - Not mandatory but selected by project partners.
- 12 B. Networking and synergies
 - 12. 1. B. Networking and synergies with projects/initiatives
- 13. B. New jobs created
- 14.B. Economic sustainability and Catalytic effect
 - 14.1. B. Revenue during or after project end, due to project outcomes
 - 14.2. B. Catalytic effect - financial - cumulative investments triggered, or finance accessed
 - 14.3.1 B. Continuation after the project end
 - 14.3.1 B. Continuation after the project-end in the same premises/area(s) as those used during the project

3 Indicator values as reported in the KPI webtool

3.1 - Project area, length and population

3.1.1 - KPI 1.5. B. Project work area

This is a mandatory indicator for all LIFE projects.

The project work area is the total spatial extent of the work area in which its actions take place. It is where the project’s budget is used to achieve objectives.

This KPI was not initially reported at the proposal stage.

Figure 1. Description and values of KPI 1.5.B for the Specific context of Murcia - WW.

Figure 2. Description and values of KPI 1.5.B for the Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

3.1.2 - KPI 1.6.B. Humans impacted by the project

This is a mandatory indicator for all LIFE projects.

This indicator measures the total number of people that are impacted by the project within the relevant context(s).

Specific context*: GENERAL

First indicator descriptor*: Choose the type of impact
Type of impact: Persons reached (via dissemination or awareness raising project-actions)

Second indicator descriptor*: Choose the type of persons impacted
Type of persons: Other persons influenced /impacted independently of the project area

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	400.00	750.00	Number of per...

Comments:
During the project it is expected to organise a series of activities to raise awareness of the project. Activities comprises info days at demo site premises, B2B meetings with potential clients, the creation of newsletters... The objective of these events is to present project progress and achievements to the project audience.
It is expected to raise awareness among 400 people although during the project and 750 people 3 years after. Note that people reached through the website are excluded in this KPI

Figure 3. Description and values of KPI 1.6.B for the General context of the project

3.2 - KPI 2.B Water (including the marine environment)

3.2.1 - KPI 2.2.B. Reduction in area or length of surface freshwater bodies or volume of groundwater whose status is affected by issues addressed in the project

This indicator describes the improvement (ecological, chemical or quantitative) in freshwater bodies (surface or groundwater bodies) as a direct result of the project's actions within the specific context.

This information is of relevance for the Water Framework Directive, the Floods Directive and the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030.

KPI 2.2.B is one of the pre-ticked KPIs for LIFE PRISTINE project due to its relation to the Water sub-priority topic. However, considering that the project is going to be developed at a pilot plant level (1 m³/h of capacity treatment), the subsequent impact at water body level will be almost neglectable. For this reason, the option 'provide values later' is ticked in the KPI webtool for both specific contexts.

3.2.2 - KPI 2.4.B. Pressure(s) or Risk(s) addressed

3.2.2.1 - KPI 2.4.2.B Water efficiency - Reduction in new water produced/supplied, due to appropriate water saving measures.

This indicator is designed to capture information on reductions in new water produced or supplied due to appropriate water saving measures. The indicator monitors the increase in water treated for reuse; saved by avoiding water loss; saved by reducing demand; or saved via other means. Values should be measured directly and should apply to the improvements from project actions within the specific context. The indicator is designed to provide information linked to the Regulation on minimum requirements for water reuse and the Water Framework Directive (WFD).

The KPI is only selected for reporting in the Specific Context of Murcia - WW. This KPI was already reported as part of the proposal (Part C) but values were related to Cehegin WWTP, the initial plant selected as wastewater treatment scenario for demonstration activities. The value reported herein is updated for Ceutí WWTP.

Specific context*:	Murcia - WW			▼
First level indicator descriptor*:	Water savings in Water Production Sector (e.g. for cleaning membranes, etc)			▼
Second level indicator descriptor & values:	Provide values later: <input type="checkbox"/>			
	Reduction in new water produced / supplied, due to appropriate water saving measures (please clarify how in the lines a - e).			
	At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
	2,920,000.00	2,911,240.00	0.00	m3/year
a.	Part of the reduction achieved through reuse of treated Urban Waste Water for agricultural irrigation.			Unit
	At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	m3/year
	0.00	8,760.00	2,920,000.00	
b.	Part of the reduction achieved through other reuse of treated Waste Water (urban, industrial, etc).			Unit
	At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	m3/year
	0.00	0.00	0.00	
c.	Part of the reduction achieved by avoiding water losses/leakages			Unit
	At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	m3/year
	0.00	0.00	0.00	
d.	Part of the reduction achieved through reduction/prevention of water demand (e.g. using processes/techniques/behaviors that are less water demanding)			Unit
	At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	m3/year
	0.00	0.00	0.00	
e.	Part of the reduction achieved through other means (other than reuse, loss/leakage reduction, or demand reduction).			Unit
	At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	m3/year
	0.00	0.00	0.00	

Figure 4. Description and values of KPI 2.4.2.B for the the Specific Context Murcia - WW.

Comments:

Ceutí WWTP is designed to treat up to 2,920,000 m3/year (project start value). Currently, Ceutí reclaimed water does not reach quality A water (It is Type C). PRISTINE solution aims to substitute tertiary treatment to attain quality A standards, so the effluent could be directly reused for irrigation.

The PRISTINE Integrated Solution is designed to treat 1m3/h and is expected to attain quality A standards, so the effluent could be directly used for irrigation. Thus, the PEV takes into account that 1m3/h reaches quality A water, reducing the amount of fresh water needed.

After 3 years it could be expected that the pilot plant could be scaled up to treat all wastewater from the secondary clarifier for direct reuse, avoiding consumption of fresh water for irrigation.

- Project start value corresponds to Ceutí WWTP treatment flow per year.
- Project-End value represents the remaining treatment flow subtracting the flow treated by PRISTINE Pilot Plant (project end value = 2920000 - 1 m3/h*24h/day*365 day/year) .
- 3 years beyond Project-End Value implies that all the flow from Ceutí WWTP could be reused directly.

3.2.3 - KPI 2.4.3.B Water Pollution - Diffuse or Point source pollution

3.2.3.1 - KPI 2.4.3.B. Water pollution - diffuse and point source pollution

This indicator is designed to capture information about the improvement in pollution loads and applies to all water bodies. According to the guide, values should be measured directly and be

applicable to improvements as a direct result of the project actions within the specific context. The indicator is designed to provide information linked to the EU Water Framework Directive (Good Ecological Status) and the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Good Environmental Status).

This is the most relevant KPI for LIFE PRISTINE, since one of its main objectives is to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water bodies. KPI values for key CECs are detailed below for the two Specific Contexts. Values have been updated to those provided in at the proposal stage. In particular, the list of CECs is updated in relation to the results obtained during the first months of the analytical campaign, in terms of compounds and values, and also for Ceuti WWTP instead of Cehegin WWTP.

MURCIA - WW

Specific context*: Murcia - WW

First indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the pollutant addressed.
CAS_58-08-2 - Caffeine

Second indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.
Point Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
6,686.80	6,670.75	668.86	g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):
Select any flag(s)

For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:
Urban waste water

Comments: Caffeine was measured at an average concentration of 13,75 µg/L and 2,29 µg/L in the influent (n=20) and effluent of the secondary treatment (n=51) in Ceuti WWTP, respectively. Thus, the current biological treatment implemented is able to eliminate caffeine, but not under the PNEC value of 1 µg/L. Thus, the current emitted caffeine to the environment in g/yer is calculated based on the total treated flow in Ceuti WWTP multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the effluent of the secondary clarifier (PSV= 2920000 m³/year*2,29 µg/L * 1g/10⁶ µg*10³L/1m³). The PRISTINE integrated solution will aim to eliminate 80% of the incoming caffeine to reach an 80% reduction of CECs concentration within the tertiary treatment, to achieve values below PNEC. Consequently, the end project value for caffeine concentration at the effluent of the PRISTINE solution will be 0,46 µg/L (2,29 µg /L effluent secondary clarifier WWTP concentration*0,2 fraction not removed), while 1 m³/h (8760 m³/year) of the total Ceuti flow will be treated by PRISTINE solution. Thus, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution (PEV= PSV-2,29*0,8 fraction removed *1g/10⁶µg*10³L/1m³*8760 m³/year). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 90% of CECs removal, thus reaching caffeine WWTP effluent concentrations of 0,23 µg/L (2,29 µg /L effluent secondary clarifier WWTP concentration*0,1 fraction not removed). It is also assumed that the PRISTINE solution could treat all the Ceuti WWTP flow, thus the reduction of CECs (BPEV=PSV-2,29 µg/L influent*0,9 fraction removed *1g/10⁶µg*10³L/1m³ *2920000 m³/year).

Figure 5. KPI values for the removal of Caffeine specific context of Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: Murcia – WW

First indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the pollutant addressed.
CAS_1071-83-6 – Glyphosate

Second indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.
Point Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:
 At the beginning: 8,438.80 At the end: 8,418.55 Beyond 3 years: 843.88 Unit: g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):
Select any flag(s)
For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:
Urban waste water

Comments: Glyphosate was measured at an average concentration of 2,94 µg/L and 2,89 µg/L in the influent (n=20) and effluent of the secondary treatment (n=51) in Ceuti WWTP, respectively. Thus, the current biological treatment implemented is not able to eliminate properly glyphosate, thus the current emitted glyphosate to the environment in g/yer is calculated based on the total treated flow in Ceuti WWTP multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the WWTP influent (PSV= 2920000 m3/year*2,94 ug/L * 1g/10^6 ug*10^3L/1m3). The PRISTINE integrated solution aims to reach an overall 80% reduction of CECs concentration within the wastewater treatment, which is consistent with the draft of the new urban wastewater directive. Consequently, the end project value for glyphosate concentration at the effluent of the PRISTINE solution will be 0,59 µg/L, while 1m3/h (8760 m3/year) of the total Ceuti flow will be treated by PRISTINE solution. Thus, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution (PEV= PSV-2,94 µg/L influent*0,8 fraction removed*1g/10^6ug*10^3L/1m3*8760 m3/year). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 90% of CECs removal, thus reaching glyphosate WWTP effluent concentrations of 0,29 µg/L. It is also assumed that the PRISTINE solution could treat all the Ceuti WWTP flow (BPEV=PSV-2,94µg/L influent*0,9 fraction removed*1g/10^6ug*10^3L/1m3 *2920000 m3/year).

Figure 6. KPI values for the removal of Glyphosate specific context of Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: Murcia – WW

First indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the pollutant addressed.
CAS_15687-27-1 – Ibuprofen

Second indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.
Point Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:
 At the beginning: 11,534.00 At the end: 11,528.46 Beyond 3 years: 1,153.40 Unit: g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):
Select any flag(s)
For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:
Urban waste water

Comments: Ibuprofen was measured at an average concentration of 7,81 µg/L and 3,95 µg/L in the influent (n=20) and effluent of the secondary treatment (n=51) in Ceuti WWTP, respectively. Thus, the current biological treatment implemented is not able to eliminate properly ibuprofen, only reaching ca. 50% removal. Thus, the current emitted ibuprofen to the environment in g/year is calculated based on the total treated flow in Ceuti WWTP multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the effluent of the secondary clarifier (PSV= 2920000 m3/year*3,95ug/L * 1g/10^6 ug*10^3L/1m3). The PRISTINE integrated solution aims to reach an overall 80% reduction of CECs concentration within the wastewater treatment, which is consistent with the draft of the new urban wastewater directive. Consequently, the end project value for ibuprofen concentration at the effluent of the PRISTINE solution will be 0,79 µg/L (3,95 µg /L influent WWTP concentration*0,2 fraction not removed), while 1m3/h (8760 m3/year) of the total Ceuti flow will be treated by PRISTINE solution. Thus, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution (PEV= PSV-3,95 µg/L * 0,8 fraction removed *1g/10^6ug*10^3L/1m3*8760 m3/year). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 90% of CECs removal, thus reaching ibuprofen WWTP effluent concentrations of 0,78 µg/L (3,95 µg /L influent WWTP concentration*0,1 fraction not removed). It is also assumed that the PRISTINE solution could treat all the Ceuti WWTP flow reducing the emission of CECs (BPEV=PSV-3,95 µg/L *0,9 fraction removed *1g/10^6ug*10^3L/1m3 *2920000 m3/year).

Figure 7. KPI values for the removal of Ibuprofen - specific context of Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: Murcia – WW

First indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the pollutant addressed.
CAS_15307-86-5 – Diclofenac

Second indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.
Point Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:
 At the beginning: 788.40 At the end: 786.51 Beyond 3 years: 78.84 Unit: g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):
Select any flag(s)
For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:
Urban waste water

Comments: Diclofenac was measured at an average concentration of 0,27 µg/L and 0,32 µg/L in the influent (n=20) and effluent of the secondary treatment (n=51) in Ceuti WWTP, respectively. Thus, the current biological treatment implemented is not able to eliminate properly diclofenac. The current emitted diclofenac to the environment in g/yer is calculated based on the total treated flow in Ceuti WWTP multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the WWTP influent (PSV= 2920000 m3/year*0,27 ug/L * 1g/10^6 ug*10^3L/1m3). The PRISTINE integrated solution aims to reach an overall 80% reduction of CECs concentration within the wastewater treatment, which is consistent with the draft of the new urban wastewater directive. Consequently, the end project value for diclofenac concentration at the effluent of the PRISTINE solution will be 0,05 µg/L, while 1m3/h (8760 m3/year) of the total Ceuti flow will be treated by PRISTINE solution. Thus, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution (PEV= PSV-0,27µg/L influent*0,8 fraction removed*1g/10^6ug*10^3L/1m3*8760 m3/year). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 90% of CECs removal, thus reaching diclofenac WWTP effluent concentrations of 0,03 µg/L. It is also assumed that the PRISTINE solution could treat all the Ceuti WWTP flow thus the overall reduction will be (BPEV=PSV-0,27µg/L influent*0,9 fraction removed*1g/10^6ug*10^3L/1m3 *2920000 m3/year).

Figure 8. KPI values for the removal of Diclofenac - Specific context of Murcia - WW.

In this case, it is remarkable that the measured value at the effluent of the secondary treatment seems to be higher than that at the measured value from the influent of the plant (average value of 0.27 µg/L vs 0.32 µg/L). This apparently anomalous value can be explained by:

- Sampling is discrete, not considering the residence time.
- There are almost two times more samples from the secondary effluent than the influent (n=51 vs n=20). Therefore, average values could be influenced by this parameter.
- The standard deviation of the average concentration is between the observed difference (0.08 for the influent and 0.09 for the effluent of the secondary treatment).

The influent sample is taken prior to the addition of effluent water from the sludge treatment. This additional flow could increase the amount of diclofenac in the secondary treatment.

Taking into account the above mentioned potential explanations, and from a conservative point of view, the measured value at the influent of 0.27 mg/L has been considered for calculating this KPI.

PAIS VASCO - DW

CAS_22204-53-1 - Naproxen

Second indicator descriptor*: ⓘ Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.

Point Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
2,365.20	2,364.98	473.04	g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):
Select any flag(s)

For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:
Urban waste water

Comments: In drinking water scenario, the expected outcome of PRISTINE Integrated Solution is to reduce CECs under the levels required for Directive 2020/2184 /EC, PNEC levels in Watch Lists (Decision 2020/1161), Directive 2013/39/EU and further if possible. In the particular case of naproxen, there is no maximum allowable concentration under the amended directives. The average detected concentration of this compound detected during the analytical campaign in Nervion River has been 50ng/l (n=24). The current treatment capacity for a standard drinking water treatment plant called Venta Alta located in the same region is $3\text{m}^3/\text{s}=94608000\text{m}^3/\text{year}$, value provided by Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizcaia (CABB) who operates the plant. Nowadays, Venta Alta income water comes from Zadorra reservoirs, but certain months along the year the water capacity of the reservoirs is not enough, which worsens with recent droughts. The aim of the project is to be able to use Nervion river instead when needed. Therefore, an estimation of 50% of Venta Alta capacity coming from Nervion river during the whole year is established for the calculations. The current emitted naproxen to the environment in g/year is calculated based on 50% of Venta Alta capacity ($47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year}$) and multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the Nervion river ($\text{PSV}=47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year} \cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \cdot 50\text{ng}/\text{L} \cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng}=2365.2\text{ g}/\text{year}$). Thus, the value already detected in the Nervion river will be reduced an 50% of the initial concentration by the end of the project ($50\text{ng}/\text{L} \cdot 50\%=25\text{ng}/\text{L}$). Consequently, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution, set to $1\text{m}^3/\text{h}$ ($8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}$). ($\text{PEV}=\text{PSV}-25\mu\text{g}/\text{L} \cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng} \cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \cdot 8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}=2364.98\text{g}/\text{year}$). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 80% reduction of the initial concentration. It remains: $50\text{ng}/\text{L} \cdot 20\%=10\text{ng}/\text{L}$, which implies $473.04\text{ g}/\text{year}$ ($47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year} \cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \cdot 10\text{ng}/\text{L} \cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng g}/\text{year}$).

Figure 9. KPI values for the removal of Naproxen - Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

CAS_58-08-2 - Caffeine

Second indicator descriptor*: ⓘ Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.

Point Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
8,514.72	8,513.93	1,702.94	g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):
Select any flag(s)

For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:
Urban waste water

Comments: In drinking water scenario, the expected outcome of PRISTINE Integrated Solution is to reduce CECs under the levels required for Directive 2020/2184 /EC, PNEC levels in Watch Lists (Decision 2020/1161), Directive 2013/39/EU and further if possible. In the particular case of caffeine, there is no maximum allowable concentration under the amended directives. The average detected concentration of this compound detected during the analytical campaign in Nervion River has been 180 ng/l (n=24). The current treatment capacity for a standard drinking water treatment plant called Venta Alta located in the same region is $3\text{m}^3/\text{s}=94608000\text{m}^3/\text{year}$, value provided by Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizcaia (CABB) who operates the plant. Nowadays, Venta Alta income water comes from Zadorra reservoirs, but certain months along the year the water capacity of the reservoirs is not enough, which worsens with recent droughts. The aim of the project is to be able to use Nervion river instead when needed. Therefore, an estimation of 50% of Venta Alta capacity coming from Nervion river during the whole year is established for the calculations. The current emitted caffeine to the environment in g/year is calculated based on 50% of Venta Alta capacity ($47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year}$) and multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the Nervion river ($\text{PSV}=47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year} \cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \cdot 180\text{ng}/\text{L} \cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng}=8514.72\text{ g}/\text{year}$). Thus, the value already detected in the Nervion river will be reduced an 50% of the initial concentration by the end of the project ($180\text{ng}/\text{L} \cdot 50\%=90\text{ng}/\text{L}$). Consequently, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution, set to $1\text{m}^3/\text{h}$ ($8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}$). ($\text{PEV}=\text{PSV}-90\mu\text{g}/\text{L} \cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng} \cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \cdot 8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}=8513.93\text{g}/\text{year}$). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 80% reduction of the initial concentration. It remains: $180\text{ng}/\text{L} \cdot 20\%=36\text{ng}/\text{L}$, which implies $1702.94\text{ g}/\text{year}$ ($47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year} \cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \cdot 36\text{ng}/\text{L} \cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng g}/\text{year}$).

Figure 10. KPI values for the removal of Caffeine - Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

CAS_1071-83-6 - Glyphosate

Second indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.

Diffuse Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
11,258.35	11,257.31	2,251.67	g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):

Agricultural

For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:

Select any flag(s)

Comments: In drinking water scenario, the expected outcome of PRISTINE Integrated Solution is to reduce CECs under the levels required for Directive 2020/2184 /EC, PNEC levels in Watch Lists (Decision 2020/1161), Directive 2013/39/EU and further if possible. In the particular case of glyphosate, the maximum allowable concentration under the amended directives is set to 398.6 ng/l. The average detected concentration of this compound detected during the analytical campaign is Nervion River has been 238ng/l (n=24). The current treatment capacity for a standard drinking water treatment plant called Venta Alta located in the same region is 3m³/s=94608000m³/year, value provided by Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizcaya (CABB) who operates the plant. Nowadays, Venta Alta income water comes from Zadorra reservoirs, but certain months along the year the water capacity of the reservoirs is not enough, which worsens with recent droughts. The aim of the project is to be able to use Nervion river instead when needed. Therefore, an estimation of 50% of Venta Alta capacity coming from Nervion river during the whole year is established for the calculations. The current emitted Glyphosate to the environment in g/year is calculated based on 50% of Venta Alta capacity (47304000m³/year) and multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the Nervion river (PSV= 47304000m³/year*10³L/1m³*238ng/L*1g/10⁹ ng=11258.35 g/year). Thus, the value already detected in the Nervion river will be reduced a 50% of the initial concentration by the end of the project (238ng/l*50%=119ng/l). Consequently, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution, set to 1m³/h (8760 m³/year). (PEV= PSV-119µg/L*1g/10⁹ng*10³L/1m³*8760 m³/year=11257.31g/year). After 3 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 80% reduction of the initial concentration. It remains: 238ng/l*20%=47.60 ng/l, which implies 2251.67 g/year (47304000m³/year*10³L/1m³*47.60ng/L*1g/10⁹ ng g/year).

Figure 11. KPI values for the removal of Glyphosate - Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

CAS_104-40-5 - 4-nonylphenol

Indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.

Diffuse Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
15,373.80	15,373.10	3,074.76	g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):

Other

For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:

Other

Comments: In drinking water scenario, the expected outcome of PRISTINE Integrated Solution is to reduce CECs under the levels required for Directive 2020/2184 /EC, PNEC levels in Watch Lists (Decision 2020/1161), Directive 2013/39/EU and further if possible. In the particular case of nonylphenol, the maximum allowable concentration under the amended directives is set to 2100 ng/l. However, the average detected concentration of this compound is Nervion River has been 325ng/l (n=24). The current treatment capacity for a standard drinking water treatment plant called Venta Alta located in the same region is 3m³/s=94608000m³/year, value provided by Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizcaya (CABB) who operates the plant. Nowadays, Venta Alta income water comes from Zadorra reservoirs, but certain months along the year the water capacity of the reservoirs is not enough, which worsens with recent droughts. The aim of the project is to be able to use Nervion river instead when needed. Therefore, an estimation of 50% of Venta Alta capacity coming from Nervion river during the whole year is established for the calculations. The current emitted nonylphenol to the environment in g/year is calculated based on 50% of Venta Alta capacity (47304000m³/year) and multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the Nervion river (PSV= 47304000m³/year*10³L/1m³*325ng/L*1g/10⁹ ng= 15373.8g/year). Thus, the value already detected in the Nervion river will be reduced a 50% of the initial concentration by the end of the project (325ng/l*50%=162.5ng/l). Consequently, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution, set to 1m³/h (8760 m³/year). (PEV= PSV-162.5µg/L*1g/10⁹ng*10³L/1m³*8760 m³/year=15373.10g/year). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 80% reduction of the initial concentration. It remains: 325ng/l*20%=65ng/l, which implies 3074.76 g/year (47304000m³/year*10³L/1m³*65ng/L*1g/10⁹ ng g/year).

Figure 12. KPI values for the removal of 4-Nonylphenol - Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

CAS_80-05-7 - Bisphenol A

Second indicator descriptor*:

Diffuse Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
11,305.66	11,304.70	4,612.14	g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):

For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:

Comments: In drinking water scenario, the expected outcome of PRISTINE Integrated Solution is to reduce CECs under the levels required for Directive 2020/2184 /EC, PNEC levels in Watch Lists (Decision 2020/1161), Directive 2013/39/EU and further if possible. In the particular case of BPA, the maximum allowable concentration under the amended directives is set to 130 ng/l. The average detected concentration of this compound detected during the analytical campaign is Nervion River has been 239ng/l (n=24). The current treatment capacity for a standard drinking water treatment plant called Venta Alta located in the same region is $3\text{m}^3/\text{s}=94608000\text{m}^3/\text{year}$, value provided by Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizcaia (CABB) who operates the plant. Nowadays, Venta Alta income water comes from Zadorra reservoirs, but certain months along the year the water capacity of the reservoirs is not enough, which worsens with recent droughts. The aim of the project is to be able to use Nervion river instead when needed. Therefore, an estimation of 50% of Venta Alta capacity coming from Nervion river during the whole year is established for the calculations. The current emitted BPA to the environment in g/year is calculated based on 50% of Venta Alta capacity ($47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year}$) and multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the Nervion river ($\text{PSV}=47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year} \times 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \times 239\text{ng}/\text{L} \times 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng}=11305.66\text{g}/\text{year}$). Thus, the value already detected in the Nervion river will be reduced to 130 ng/l by the end of the project ($239-130=109\text{ng}/\text{l}$). Consequently, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution, set to $1\text{m}^3/\text{h}$ ($8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}$). ($\text{PEV}=\text{PSV}-109\mu\text{g}/\text{L} \times 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng} \times 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \times 8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}=11304.70\text{g}/\text{year}$). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 25% reduction of the maximum allowable concentration ($130 \times 75\%=97.5\text{ng}/\text{l}$). It remains $97.5\text{ng}/\text{l}$, wich implies $4612.14\text{g}/\text{year}$ ($47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year} \times 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \times 98\text{ng}/\text{L} \times 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng g}/\text{year}$).

Figure 13. KPI values for the removal of Bisphenol-A- Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

CAS_15687-27-1 - Ibuprofen

Second indicator descriptor*:

Diffuse Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
7,568.64	7,567.94	1,513.73	g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):

For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:

Comments: In drinking water scenario, the expected outcome of PRISTINE Integrated Solution is to reduce CECs under the levels required for Directive 2020/2184 /EC, PNEC levels in Watch Lists (Decision 2020/1161), Directive 2013/39/EU and further if possible. In the particular case of ibuprofen, there is no maximum allowable concentration under the amended directives. The average detected concentration of this compound detected during the analytical campaign is Nervion River has been 160ng/l (n=24). The current treatment capacity for a standard drinking water treatment plant called Venta Alta located in the same region is $3\text{m}^3/\text{s}=94608000\text{m}^3/\text{year}$, value provided by Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizcaia (CABB) who operates the plant. Nowadays, Venta Alta income water comes from Zadorra reservoirs, but certain months along the year the water capacity of the reservoirs is not enough, which worsens with recent droughts. The aim of the project is to be able to use Nervion river instead when needed. Therefore, an estimation of 50% of Venta Alta capacity coming from Nervion river during the whole year is established for the calculations. The current emitted ibuprofen to the environment in g/year is calculated based on 50% of Venta Alta capacity ($47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year}$) and multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the Nervion river ($\text{PSV}=47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year} \times 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \times 160\text{ng}/\text{L} \times 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng}=7568.64\text{g}/\text{year}$). Thus, the value already detected in the Nervion river will be reduced an 50% of the initial concentration by the end of the project ($160\text{ng}/\text{l} \times 50\%=80\text{ng}/\text{l}$). Consequently, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution, set to $1\text{m}^3/\text{h}$ ($8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}$). ($\text{PEV}=\text{PSV}-80\mu\text{g}/\text{L} \times 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng} \times 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \times 8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}=7567.94\text{g}/\text{year}$). After 3 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 80% reduction of the initial concentration. It remains: $160\text{ng}/\text{l} \times 20\%=32\text{ng}/\text{l}$, which implies $1513.73\text{g}/\text{year}$ ($47304000\text{m}^3/\text{year} \times 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3 \times 32\text{ng}/\text{L} \times 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng g}/\text{year}$).

Figure 14. KPI values for the removal of Ibuprofen - Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

CAS_15307-86-5 - Diclofenac

Second indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of pollution addressed.

Diffuse Source pollution

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
1,419.12	1,418.99	282.82	g/year

Indicator flags: For diffuse source pollution choose the Source type(s):

Other

For point source pollution choose the Source type of the pollution:

Other

Comments:

In drinking water scenario, the expected outcome of PRISTINE Integrated Solution is to reduce CECs under the levels required for Directive 2020/2184 /EC, PNEC levels in Watch Lists (Decision 2020/1161), Directive 2013/39/EU and further if possible. In the particular case of diclofenac, the maximum allowable concentration under the amended directives is set to 250 ng/l. The average detected concentration of this compound detected during the analytical campaign is Nervion River has been 30 ng/l (n=24). The current treatment capacity for a standard drinking water treatment plant called Venta Alta located in the same region is $3\text{m}^3/\text{s}=9460800\text{m}^3/\text{year}$, value provided by Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizcaia (CABB) who operates the plant. Nowadays, Venta Alta income water comes from Zadorra reservoirs, but certain months along the year the water capacity of the reservoirs is not enough, which worsens with recent droughts. The aim of the project is to be able to use Nervion river instead when needed. Therefore, an estimation of 50% of Venta Alta capacity coming from Nervion river during the whole year is established for the calculations. The current emitted diclofenac to the environment in g/year is calculated based on 50% of Venta Alta capacity ($4730400\text{m}^3/\text{year}$) and multiplied by the measured CEC concentration in the Nervion river ($\text{PSV}=4730400\text{m}^3/\text{year}\cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3\cdot 30\text{ng}/\text{L}\cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng}=1419.12\text{g}/\text{year}$). Thus, the value already detected in the Nervion river will be reduced an 50% of the initial concentration by the end of the project ($30\text{ng}/\text{L}\cdot 50\%=15\text{ng}/\text{L}$). Consequently, the reduction of CECs emitted to the environment will be reduced from the original PSV based on the total flow treated by the PRISTINE solution, set to $1\text{m}^3/\text{h}$ ($8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}$). ($\text{PEV}=\text{PSV}\cdot 15\mu\text{g}/\text{L}\cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng}\cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3\cdot 8760\text{m}^3/\text{year}=1418.99\text{g}/\text{year}$). After 3/5 years it is expected that the optimization of the scaling up could reach a 80% reduction of the initial concentration. It remains: $30\text{ng}/\text{L}\cdot 20\%=6\text{ng}/\text{L}$, which implies $283.82\text{g}/\text{year}$ ($4730400\text{m}^3/\text{year}\cdot 10^3\text{L}/1\text{m}^3\cdot 6\text{ng}/\text{L}\cdot 1\text{g}/10^9\text{ng}\text{g}/\text{year}$).

Figure 15. KPI values for the removal of Diclofenac - Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

3.3 - KPI 4.B Resource efficiency and Waste

3.3.1 - KPI 4.1.B Energy

3.3.1.1 - KPI 4.1.1.B Primary energy consumption reduction

This indicator monitors the contribution of LIFE projects to the reduction in the amount of primary energy required to provide a service and/or produce a product.

The indicator is designed to provide information linked to the EU clean energy package (CEP) and more specifically to the Energy Performance in Buildings and Energy Efficiency Directives which are an integral part of the CEP.

The value of this KPI is updated from that reported in the Proposal (Part C) to reflect the values for Ceutí WWTP once the final location for wastewater demonstration activities has been selected. Besides, values for the drinking water demonstration activities are provided.

Specific context*: Murcia - WW

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the Energy sources.

Multiple sources

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning: 1,051.20 | At the end: 1,050.25 | Beyond 3 years: 669.05 | Unit: MWh/year

Indicator flags: Choose the relevant Energy consumption sector(s): Industry sector

Comments: Project start value considers the energy consumption needed for Ceutí WWTP treatment design flow (2,920,000 m³/year) to remove CECS with a conventional tertiary treatment such as RO membranes (0,36 kWh/m³) for CEC removal (PSV= 2920000 m³/year*0,36 kWh/m³*1GWh/1000000 kWh). PRISTINE Integrated Solution nanofiltration will entail a reduction of 30% of the energy required (0,36*0,7 = 0,252 kWh/m³) thanks to the more energy efficient nanofiltration membranes. Thus, at the project end value PRISTINE solution will treat 1m³/h of the total flow rate with an energy consumption of 0,252 kWh/m³, while the rest of the flow rate (2911240m³/year) is still treated with not that efficient technologies (PEV=2911240 m³/year*0,36 kWh/m³*1GWh/1000000 kWh - 1m³/h*24h/day*365day/year*0,252 kWh/m³*1GWh/1000000kwh). After 3 years all Ceutí WWTP design flow could be treated with an additional 5% energy saving could be foreseen reaching an energy consumption of 0,2394 kWh/m³ thanks to the optimization of operational parameters when scaled up (3 BPEV =2920000 m³/year* 0,2394 kWh/m³*1GWh/1000000 kWh)

Figure 16. KPI values for Primary energy consumption reduction - Specific context of Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: País Vasco - DW

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the Energy sources.

Multiple sources

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning: 6,622.56 | At the end: 6,622.19 | Beyond 3 years: 4,404.00 | Unit: MWh/year

Indicator flags: Choose the relevant Energy consumption sector(s): Industry sector

Comments: The current treatment capacity for a standard drinking water treatment plant called Venta Alta located in the same region is 3m³/s=9460800m³/year, value provided by Consorcio de Aguas Bilbao Bizkaia (CABB) who operates the plant. Nowadays, Venta Alta income water comes from Zadorra reservoirs, but certain months along the year the water capacity of the reservoirs is not enough, which worsens with recent droughts. The aim of the project is to be able to use Nervión river instead when needed. Therefore, an estimation of 50% of Venta Alta capacity coming from Nervión river during the whole year is established for the calculations. Project start value considers the energy consumption needed for 50% Venta Alta treatment design flow (47304000 m³/year) to remove CECS with a conventional tertiary treatment such as RO membranes (an estimation of 0.14 kWh/m³ is established based on Acciona experience) for CEC removal (PSV= 47304000 m³/year*0.14 kWh/m³*1GWh/1000000 kWh=6.62256GWh/year). PRISTINE Integrated Solution nanofiltration will entail a reduction of 30% of the energy required (0.14*0.7 = 0.098 kWh/m³) thanks to the more energy efficient nanofiltration membranes. Thus, at the project end value PRISTINE solution will treat 1m³/h (8760 m³/year) of the total flow rate with an energy consumption of 0.098 kWh/m³, while the rest of the flow rate (47304000-8760)m³/year is still treated with not that efficient technologies (PEV=(47304000-8760)m³/year*0.14 kWh/m³*1GWh/1000000 kWh + 8760m³/year*0.098kwh/m³*1GWh/1000000Kwh=6.62219GWh/year). After 3 years all Venta Alta design flow could be treated with an additional 5% energy saving could be foreseen reaching an energy consumption of 0.0931 kWh/m³ (0.098*0.95=0.0931kWh/m³) thanks to the optimization of operational parameters when scaled up (3 BPEV =47304000 m³/year* 0.0931 kWh/m³*1GWh/1000000 kWh=4.4040 GWh/year). This 5% additional saving is equivalent to a 33.5% of energy reduction of the original situation (0.14*0.665=0.0931 kWh/m³).

Figure 17. KPI values for Primary energy consumption reduction - Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

3.4 - KPI 8.B Climate change Mitigation

3.4.1 - KPI 8.1.B Reduction in Greenhouse Gas emissions

The scope of this indicator is to quantify the project’s net mitigation impact, which is the reduction in the carbon footprint of the project’s demonstration actions, in terms of CO₂eq. It refers to the total net amount of CO₂eq reduced per year. As an explanatory element, the

project should also provide the reduction of CO₂eq normalised per unit of project product/outcome. In this particular case, per m³ produced.

PRISTINE projects is focused on reducing CO₂ emissions from energy savings. This KPI was not selected for reporting at the proposal stage so the first snapshot is provided as part of this document.

Specific context*: Murcia - WW

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the Main source(s) of emissions. Industrial production / processes

Indicator values:

Provide values later:	At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
<input type="checkbox"/>	262.80	262.56	174.76	Tons of CO2e...
	0.09	0.09	0.05	kg CO2eq / u...

Indicator flags: Choose the relevant GHGs: CO₂

Comments:

Based on KPI 4.1.1.B the energy consumption per year will be as follows: PSV = 1,05120 GWh/year , PEV=1,05025 GWh/year, BPEV=0,69905 GWh/year. The energy consumptions calculated for all scenarios are multiplied by the average CO₂ emissions per kWh of energy generated of Spain, which according to https://canviclimatic.gencat.cat/es/actua/factors_demissio_associats_a_lenergia/ was 250 ton CO₂ eq./GWh.

Thus, the CO₂ emissions reductions can be calculated as follow:
 PSV=1,05120 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh = 262,80 ton CO₂ eq/year
 PEV=1,05025 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh = 262,56 ton CO₂ eq/year
 BPEV=0,69905 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh = 174,76 ton CO₂ eq/year

 Total ton CO₂/year CO₂ is calculated per unit of water treated, which is m³, assuming Ceuti WWTP design flow (2920000 m³/year).
 PSV = 1,051 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh = 262,8 ton CO₂ eq/year / 2.920.000 m³/year*10³kg/1ton = 0,09000 kgco₂/m³
 PEV=1,050 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh = 262,6 ton CO₂ eq/year / 2.920.000 m³/year*10³kg/1ton=0,089992 kgCO₂/ m³
 BPEV=0,686 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh = 174,76 ton CO₂ eq/year / 2.920.000 m³/year*10³kg/1ton = 0,05985 kgCO₂/m³

Figure 18. KPI values for reduction of GHG emissions - Specific context of Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: Pais Vasco - DW

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the Main source(s) of emissions. Industrial production / processes

Indicator values:

Provide values later:	At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
<input type="checkbox"/>	1,655.64	1,655.54	1,101.00	Tons of CO2e...
	0.03	0.03	0.02	kg CO2eq / u...

Indicator flags: Choose the relevant GHGs: CO₂

Comments:

The energy consumptions calculated for all scenarios are multiplied by the average CO₂ emissions per kWh of energy generated of Spain, which according to https://canviclimatic.gencat.cat/es/actua/factors_demissio_associats_a_lenergia/ was 250 ton CO₂ eq./GWh.

Thus, the CO₂ emissions reductions can be calculated as follow:
 PSV =6,62256 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh;
 PEV=6.622219 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh;
 BPEV=4.404002 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh.

 CO₂ is calculated per unit of water treated, which is m³, assuming 50% Venta Alta treatment design flow (47,304,000 m³/year).
 PSV =6.6226 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh/47304000 m³/year*10³kg/1ton = 0.0350 kgco₂/m³
 PEV=6.6222 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh/47304000 m³/year*10³kg/1ton = 0.0349 kgco₂/m³
 BPEV=4.4040 GWh/year * 250 ton CO₂eq/GWh/47304000 m³/year*10³kg/1ton = 0.0233 kgco₂/m³

Figure 19. KPI values for reduction of GHG emissions - Specific context of País Vasco - DW.

3.5 - KPI 11. B. Information and awareness

3.5.1 - KPI 11.1. B. Website

This KPI is created to assess the impact of the project through the specific website. It is calculated using the General context, as follows:

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: No. of unique visits

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	10,000.00	12,500.00	Number of uni...

Comments: The target Number of unique visites to the website is set in 10,000 at the end of the project. Once the project finishes, it is expected an increase of 25 % in the next 3/5 years, thus, 12500 unique visits. Visits will be followed using Google Analytics.

Figure 20. KPI values for the project impact through website.

The values remain the same as those indicated in at the proposal stage.

3.5.2 - KPI 11.2 B. Other tools for reaching/raising awareness

This indicator will indicate where the different outreach/ awareness-raising outputs were developed/positioned. Values indicated in the tables below at ‘The end of the project’ are in line with those described in the proposal. Additional estimations for 3 years beyond the project, and KPIs values for the number of patents and trademarks generated as a consequence of the project are provided here for the first time.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the other tools for reaching/raising awareness.
 Number of articles in print media (e.g. newspaper and magazine articles)

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	8.00	10.00	Number of out...

Comments: As a consequence of project activities, 8 publications in trade magazines, newspaper or radio interviews will be generated. After the project, the figure will increase in two.

Figure 21. KPI values related to the # of articles in print media.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the other tools for reaching/raising awareness.
Number of different displayed information created (posters, information boards)

Indicator values: Provide values later:
 At the beginning: 0.00 At the end: 3.00 Beyond 3 years: 3.00 Unit: Number of out...

Comments: Three project posters will be created, one at the beginning of the project, one describing the results in wastewater scenario, and one describing the results in the drinking water scenario.

Figure 22. KPI values related to the # different displayed information.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the other tools for reaching/raising awareness.
Number of events/exhibitions organised

Indicator values: Provide values later:
 At the beginning: 0.00 At the end: 3.00 Beyond 3 years: 3.00 Unit: Number of out...

Comments: The project foresees organising 3 awareness campaigns in months 24, 36 and 48. Two of them will take place together with demo site visits.

Figure 23. KPI values related to the # events/exhibitions.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the other tools for reaching/raising awareness.
Number of different publications made (Journal/conference)

Indicator values: Provide values later:
 At the beginning: 0.00 At the end: 8.00 Beyond 3 years: 12.00 Unit: Number of out...

Comments: During the project it is expected to participate in 4 conferences in which the results will be presented. In addition, project results will be published in 4 different scientific journals.

Figure 24. KPI values related to the # publications in scientific media.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the other tools for reaching/raising awareness.
Number of trademarks submitted

Indicator values: Provide values later:
 At the beginning: 0.00 At the end: 2.00 Beyond 3 years: 2.00 Unit: Number of out...

Comments: The PRISTINE technology will be identified by a trademark, as a unique solution. The new UV-LED reactor will be identified by a trademark as well.

Figure 25. KPI values related to the # trademarks.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the other tools for reaching/raising awareness.

Number of patents submitted

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	1.00	1.00	Number of out...

Comments: It is expected to fill and submit an additional patent, tentatively focused on the use of capsules for CECs adsorption.

Figure 26. KPI values related to the # patents.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the other tools for reaching/raising awareness.

Other distinct media products created (e.g. different videos/broadcast/leaflets)

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	4.00	5.00	Number of out...

Comments: As part of project activities it is expected to create:
-2 video
-2 brochures, 250 copies disseminated each.

Figure 27. KPI values related to other distinct media products.

3.6 -KPI 12 B. Networking and synergies

3.6.1 - KPI 12.1.B. Networking and synergies with projects

This KPI is mandatory for all LIFE projects.

Projects should report on networking with other projects or initiatives under this KPI. They should provide information on the number and type of projects/initiatives (not individuals) with which their project has interacted. The General context is used for this purpose. Values provided are based on those described in the proposal.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the type of projects / initiatives and provide values below

Other projects or initiatives (nationally/regionally/privately funded; to be specified in the commen...)

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	2.00	4.00	No. of project...

Indicator flags: Networking outcomes achieved: Knowledge exchange X

Networking tools used with other projects/initiatives: B2B meetings X

Comments: During the project, it is expected to create synergies with 2 projects or initiatives related to CECS removal in water. 3 years after the project the number will increase to reach a final value of 4.

Figure 28. KPI values related to the other projects and initiatives to which the project expects to create synergies.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the type of projects / initiatives and provide values below

LIFE projects

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	4.00	6.00	No. of project...

Indicator flags: Networking outcomes achieved: Knowledge exchange X

Networking tools used with other projects/initiatives: Experience exchange meetings X

Comments: As part of project networking activities, it is expected to create synergies with 4 LIFE projects during the execution of PRISTINE. In the next 3 years, this number will increase up to 6.

Figure 29. KPI values related to LIFE projects to which the project expects to create synergies.

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: Choose the type of projects / initiatives and provide values below

Horizon Europe Projects

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	2.00	3.00	No. of project...

Indicator flags: Networking outcomes achieved: Knowledge exchange

Networking tools used with other projects/initiatives: Experience exchange meetings

Comments: As part of project networking activities, it is expected to create synergies with 2 European projects during the execution of PRISTINE. In the next 3 years, this number will increase up to 3.

Figure 30. KPI values related to Horizon projects to which the project expects to create synergies.

3.7 - KPI 13. B. New jobs created

This is a mandatory indicator for all LIFE projects to indicate the new jobs created by the project. Values provided in this document are a more accurate updated of those reported as part of the proposal (Part C).

Specific context*: GENERAL

Indicator descriptor*: New jobs created

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	3.00	5.00	No. of FTE

Indicator flags: Choose the Age group: 25-54

Choose the Gender of the employee(s): Female, Male

Choose the Level of education: Tertiary (ISCED levels 5-8), Upper secondary, Post-secondary and non-tertiary (ISCED levels 3-4)

Choose the Specificities of the employees: Skilled

Other specificities: Select any flag(s)

Comments: Three people have been contracted for the project (since de beginning) 3/5 years beyond the project it is expected that 5 new jobs will be created, associated to the replication and transferability of project results

Figure 31. KPI values related to job creation during and in 3 years beyond the project.

3.8 - KPI 14.B. Economic sustainability and Catalytic effect

3.8.1 - KPI 14.1.B. Revenue during or after project end, due to project outcomes.

This KPI shows cumulative revenues during or after the end of the project, due to the project outcomes/actions.

Specific context*: Murcia - WW

Indicator descriptor*: Revenue from fees

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	0.00	29,200.00	€

Comments:

During the project there won't be any revenue due to the pilot scale of the activities. Once it finishes and if implemented at full scale in Ceuti WWTP (8,000 m3/d), the revenues will come back as part of the water tariff, becoming extremely difficult to provide an accurate value. It will depend on the mainstream treatment and many other different factors, but, to provide a very rough number, let's assume that:

Beyond 3 years 8,000 m3/d are being treated with PRISTINE and 0,01 euro/m3 is linked to PRISTINE, resulting in 80 euro/d, in 3 years, an amount of 29,200 euro (in year 3 after the project). (CAPEX to install PRISTINE is excluded)

It is assumed that plant will be operative in year 3, this is why values for one single year are reported.

Figure 32. KPI values related to project revenues - Specific context of Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: Pais Vasco - DW

Indicator descriptor*: Revenue from fees

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	0.00	236,520.00	€

Comments:

During the project there won't be any revenue due to the pilot scale of the activities. Once it finishes and if implemented at full scale, the revenues will come back as part of the water tariff, becoming extremely difficult to provide an accurate value. To provide a very rough number, let's assume that:

Beyond 3 years, the project results are implemented in ETAP Venta Alta, with a treatment capacity of 259,200 m3/d, half of it considered in the project. Assuming that benefits of 0,005 euro/m3 are linked to PRISTINE, it would result in 1,296 euro/d, and of 473,040 euro (in year 3 after the project) (CAPEX to install PRISTINE is excluded). (129,600 m3/d*0.005 euro/m3 *365 days/year = 473,040 euro/year).

It is assumed that plant will be operative in year 3, this is why values for one single year are reported.

Figure 33. KPI values related to project revenues - Specific context of Pais Vasco - DW.

3.8.2 - KPI 14.2.B. Catalytic effect - financial - cumulative investments triggered, or finance accessed

This indicator is used to report additional finance accessed or investments that PRISTINE project may trigger, which are aligned with the objectives of your LIFE project (and the LIFE programme). "Additional" implies budget from other EU financial instruments and/or other public or private sources.

Specific context*: Murcia - WW

Indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of Investment triggered or finance accessed

Beneficiary own contribution (other than project co-financing and not included in project budget)

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	30,000.00	300,000.00	€

Comments: During the project the additional investment will be dedicated to carry out additional analytical campaigns in other WWTP operated by ACCIONA. Once the project ends, it is expected to upgrade existing facilities with some of the PRISTINE results.

Figure 34. KPI values additional investments triggered by the PRISTINE project - Specific context Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: Pais Vasco - DW

Indicator descriptor*: Please indicate the type of Investment triggered or finance accessed

Beneficiary own contribution (other than project co-financing and not included in project budget)

Indicator values: Provide values later:

At the beginning	At the end	Beyond 3 years	Unit
0.00	25,000.00	100,000.00	€

Comments: During the project the additional investment will be dedicated to carry out additional analytical campaigns in the demo site. Once the project ends, the results could be implemented (total or partially) in a WTP operated or constructed by ACCIONA. Such additional contribution could be estimated in 100,000 euro

Figure 35. KPI values additional investments triggered by the PRISTINE project - Specific context País Vasco - DW.

3.8.3 - KPI 14.3.1B. Continuation/replication/transfer after the project end

3.8.3.1 - KPI 14.3.1.b. Continuation in the same premises/area(s) as those used during the project

In this KPI, it is indicated if the methods, techniques, prototypes or practices used/developed during the project will continue to be used after the project end in the same premises/area/context as during the project. This is a mandatory indicator for all LIFE projects. KPI values provided below are those describe in the proposal, Section 2.3 Sustainability of project results.

Specific context*: Murcia - WW

Indicator descriptor*: Please indicate whether the project actions and/or results are to be continued and at what level

Continuation at same scale (compared to the scale during project implementation)

Comments: Following LIFE PRISTINE development, project partners are committed to continue with further demonstration activities for minimum 5 years, with two main emphases: broaden CECs shortlist of monitored component and increase the % of total CECs reduction.

Figure 36. Explanation about how activities will continue after the project and at the same scale - specific context of Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: Murcia – WW

Indicator descriptor*: **Please indicate whether the project actions and/or results are to be continued and at what level**
Continuation at higher scale (compared to the scale during project implementation)

Comments: PRISTINE Integrated Solution is expected to be ready for full scale implementation after 3 years from the end of the project. Previous to this step, activities to reach an equivalent TRL 9 should be accomplished. To this end, LIFE PRISTINE results will be detailed in a dossier created following ACC's technology transfer corporate procedure. This dossier, together with operation manuals, normalisation sheets and design guidelines will be transferred to ACC's Technical Department for scale-up, final process design and cost optimisation. The output of this stage is: 1) a normalised data sheet where all equipment and parts are detailed and 2) design/operation guidelines. Corresponding exploitation agreements among project beneficiaries will be drafted and signed, to ensure proper exploitation of the integrated solution, which will be done by ACCIONA including project beneficiaries as preferential providers of the individual unitary processes. For the PRISTINE Integrated Solution, ACC's Business Development department will seek for market opportunities and corresponding proposals, submitting LIFE PRISTINE project results to bids, launched according to market needs (see Section 2.5). In parallel, direct sales channels of XYLEM and NXF will be used for reaching the market and ensuring a proper market penetration, and technology transfer activities from EUT launched related to encapsulated adsorbents technology.

Figure 37. Explanation about how activities will continue after the project and at a higher scale - specific context of Murcia - WW.

Specific context*: País Vasco – DW

Indicator descriptor*: **Please indicate whether the project actions and/or results are to be continued and at what level**
Continuation at same scale (compared to the scale during project implementation)

Comments: Following LIFE PRISTINE development, project partners are committed to continue with further demonstration activities for minimum 5 years, with two main emphases: broaden CECs shortlist of monitored component and increase the % of total CECs reduction.

Figure 38. Explanation about how activities will continue after the project and at the same scale - specific context of País Vasco - DW.

Specific context*: País Vasco – DW

Indicator descriptor*: **Please indicate whether the project actions and/or results are to be continued and at what level**
Continuation at higher scale (compared to the scale during project implementation)

Comments: PRISTINE Integrated Solution is expected to be ready for full scale implementation after 3 years from the end of the project. Previous to this step, activities to reach an equivalent TRL 9 should be accomplished. To this end, LIFE PRISTINE results will be detailed in a dossier created following ACC's technology transfer corporate procedure. This dossier, together with operation manuals, normalisation sheets and design guidelines will be transferred to ACC's Technical Department for scale-up, final process design and cost optimisation. The output of this stage is: 1) a normalised data sheet where all equipment and parts are detailed and 2) design/operation guidelines. Corresponding exploitation agreements among project beneficiaries will be drafted and signed, to ensure proper exploitation of the integrated solution, which will be done by ACCIONA including project beneficiaries as preferential providers of the individual unitary processes. For the PRISTINE Integrated Solution, ACC's Business Development department will seek for market opportunities and corresponding proposals, submitting LIFE PRISTINE project results to bids, launched according to market needs (see Section 2.5). In parallel, direct sales channels of XYLEM and NXF will be used for reaching the market and ensuring a proper market penetration, and technology transfer activities from EUT launched related to encapsulated adsorbents technology.

Figure 39. Explanation about how activities will continue after the project and at a higher scale - specific context of País Vasco - DW.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provides a detailed description of the key KPI selected to assess the impact of the LIFE PRISTINE project. Beyond mandatory KPIs, a series of additional KPIs have been selected so as the impact in terms of technical, environmental and socioeconomic aspects can be monitored. The selected set of KPIs is complete and sufficient to assess all these aspects.

Values provided in this deliverable has been updated after the first year of the project. The document will be updated for each periodic report and once the project finishes.

5 ANNEXES

The latest KPI project data snapshot extracted from the KPIS webtool is annexed as part of a zip file.